

NATURAL FLAVONES. PART III. ON THE CONSTITUTION OF TAMBULIN.

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From the fruits of *Zanthoxylum acanthopodium* DC., two yellow crystalline substances have been isolated in poor yields. One of these, named tambulin, $C_{18}H_{16}O_7$, has been shown to be a dihydroxytrimethoxyflavone. Alkaline hydrolysis of tambulin gives anisic acid. Dimethyltambulin is not identical with tangeretin and tambulin is either 5 : 7-dihydroxy-3 : 8 : 4'-trimethoxyflavone or 5 : 7-dihydroxy-4' : 6 : 8-trimethoxyflavone.

Zanthoxylum acanthopodium DC. (N.O. *Rutaceae*) is a well known indigenous drug of the East. In Bengal the fruits are known as *Tambul*. According to Ayurveda 'the fruit is sweetish, bitter, hot; tasty and digestible; appetiser; anthelmintic; removes *kapha* and *vata*, pain, tumours and abdominal troubles; useful in eye and ear diseases, diseases of the lips, headache, heaviness, leucoderma, asthma, troubles of the spleen, difficult micturation.' According to the Yunani system of medicine, 'the seeds are tonic, useful in diarrhoea; carminative, bechic, pectoral; good in brain diseases and insanity; useful in stomatitis; strengthen the liver; purify the blood; remove foul smell from mouth.' In Indo-China the aromatic seeds are considered sudorific and febrifuge.

The essential oil, which is present to the extent of 1.2 per cent, has been the subject of an investigation by Simonsen and Rau (*Indian Forest Records*, 1922, 9, 111). The chief constituents of the oil are dipentene, methyl cinnamate and linalool. Other constituents of the fruits do not seem to have been investigated. The present paper deals with two crystalline colouring matters of the fruits, which have been isolated. These have been named tambulin and tambulol.

Tambulin (yield 0.006 %) forms bright yellow plates, m.p. 205°. It is easily soluble in cold dilute aqueous alkali with a deep yellow colour, and the alkaline solution is stable to aerial oxidation. Ferric chloride imparts a dark olive-green colour to an alcoholic solution of tambulin. Evidently it is phenolic in character. The pale yellow solution of tambulin in absolute alcohol turns orange on the addition of a drop of concentrated aqueous lead acetate solution, and an orange precipitate is thrown down on dilution with water. Alkaline *o*-dinitrobenzene (Bose, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, Sir P. C. Rây 70th Birthday Volume, p. 65) or chloropentamine cobaltchloride (Shibata and Hattori, *Acta Phytochim.*, 1930, 8, 117) have no action on tambulin. It dissolves in hot concentrated hydrochloric acid

with a yellow colour, evidently due to the formation of an oxonium salt. If this solution be diluted with alcohol and treated with metallic magnesium, a beautiful rose-red colour is immediately produced. These properties indicate that tambulin is a hydroxyflavone.

Tambulin contains methoxy groups, and the analytical data are in agreement with the formula, $C_{15}H_{13}O_2(OH)_2(OMe)_3$. It gives the expected diacetyl derivative. Hydrolysis of tambulin with 20% alcoholic potassium hydroxide gives products from which a colourless crystalline acid, m.p. $179-80^\circ$, has been isolated. Its analytical data point to the formula, $C_6H_4(OMe)CO_2H$ and it has been identified as anisic acid. The partial formula for tambulin may, therefore, be written as (I).

The other products of hydrolysis could not be isolated as sufficient material was not available for hydrolysis. Since one of the methoxy groups is present in the phenyl nucleus, the two OH groups as also the remaining two OMe groups must be in the benzopyrone nucleus. One of the OH groups may be assumed to be in position 5, since in partially methylated polyhydroxyflavones, the OH group in position 5 is not, as a rule, found in the methylated condition.* The second OH group cannot be in position 3, owing to the stability of an alkaline solution of tambulin to aerial oxidation. This OH group must be in position 7, because, otherwise tambulin would have a structure having OH groups in *ortho*- or *para*-positions to each other, and would consequently show reducing action towards *o*-dinitrobenzene and chloropentamine cobaltchloride, which was not found to be the case (*vide supra*). Hence three alternative formulæ for tambulin are possible, namely (II), (III) and (IV). The demethylated products from (II) and (III) should give a positive Bargellini's test, which is characteristic of three contiguous OH groups in positions 5, 6 and 7 of a benzopyrone nucleus (Bargellini, *Gazzetta*, 1919, **49**, 47;

* The only exception appears to be calycopterin (=thapsin), in which, according to the suggestion made by Mahal and Venkataraman (*Current Sci.*, 1935, **4**, 311), the 5 position carries a methoxyl group and the 6 position a hydroxyl. Further work has shown that the suggested structure must be confirmed by additional evidence which is now being sought (Venkataraman, *private communication*).

Baker, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1030; Baker, Nodzu and Robinson, *ibid.*, 1929, 83).

Tambulin on demethylation by means of hydriodic acid gives a product, an alcoholic solution of which yields a bluish green flocculent precipitate with freshly prepared sodium amalgam. This positive Bargellini's test can be expected from the demethylation products of both (II) and (III). If the formula (II) represent the correct structure of tambulin, then its dimethyl ether should be identical with tangeretin (Nelson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 1392; Goldsworthy and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 46). To settle this point we methylated tambulin with an excess of diazomethane. The ether, purified by distillation in high vacuum and crystallisation, melts at 160° (uncorr.), whereas the recorded m.p. of tangeretin is 154° (corr.). Moreover, demethylated tangeretin develops a green colour quickly, which is not found to be the case with the demethylated product of tambulin. These differences in m.p. and colour suggest that dimethyltambulin is different from tangeretin. A direct comparison of these two substances has, moreover, been possible through the kindness of Dr. E. K. Nelson, to whom our best thanks are due. Although the outward appearances of the compounds are very similar, a mixture of the two melted between 146° and 151°. The formula (II) for tambulin had consequently to be rejected.

The formula (IV) has already been left out of consideration, since its demethylated product should not be expected to give a positive Bargellini's test. We, however, wanted to confirm this point. Quite recently the compound (VIII) has been isolated in the form of a glucoside, herbacitrin, from the flowers of certain cotton plants (Neelkantam and Seshadri, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1937, **A**, **5**, 357) and the aglucone (VIII) has been synthesised by Goldsworthy and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 56). Prof. T. R. Seshadri kindly carried out Bargellini's test with herbacetin at our request, and informed us that the test was positive, the colour of the precipitate being bluish green (*cf.* Rao and Seshadri, *Current Sci.*, 1938, **7**, 228). This was rather unexpected, since a positive Bargellini's test has always been associated with 5:6:7-trihydroxybenzopyrones (*vide supra*). The observation of Prof. Seshadri, which is very significant, shows that a herbacetin type of formula for tambulin, namely (IV), is not excluded. As a matter of fact the difference in m.p. of herbacetin pentamethyl ether and tambulin dimethyl ether is only 2—4°. A direct comparison of these two substances has not yet been possible for want of an authentic specimen of herbacetin pentamethyl ether.

(VIII)

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Isolation of Tambulin.—The fruits of *Zanthoxylum acanthopodium* DC. were supplied by a local dealer in drugs and were identified by Mr. N. Mitra, Curator, Royal Botanic Garden, Sibpur, to whom our best thanks are due. 500 G. of coarsely powdered fruits were refluxed with a litre of rectified spirit for 2 hours and filtered hot. The process of extraction was repeated four times, using the same volume of fresh solvent in each operation. The combined filtrates which had a brown yellow colour, were concentrated on the water-bath under reduced pressure. The brown oily residue was then poured into 500 c.c. of petroleum ether, when a tar separated out. The petroleum ether layer (A) was separated from the tar (B) by decantation and allowed to stand in a closed vessel for several weeks at the room temperature. The tar (B) was dissolved in rectified spirit and allowed to stand.

Small yellow crystals gradually separated out from Fraction A and were collected after 4 weeks. The crude product was washed with a small quantity of cold rectified spirit to remove tarry matters and then dissolved in chloroform, in which it freely dissolves. The chloroform solution was filtered and the solvent completely removed. The bright yellow crystalline residue was twice crystallised from acetone and then thrice from glacial acetic acid, when deep yellow plates, m.p. 205° , were obtained. Further crystallisations did not raise the m.p. The yield was 0.75 g. from 12 kg. of fruits. (Found: C, 62.29, 62.20; H, 4.88, 4.73; OMe, 26.44. $C_{18}H_{16}O_7$ requires C, 62.79; H, 4.65; OMe, 27.04 per cent).

Tambulin dissolves freely in chloroform, benzene, acetone and hot glacial acetic acid; it is sparingly soluble in alcohol and ethyl acetate, and insoluble in petroleum ether.

Isolation of Tambulol.—From the alcoholic solution of (B), a small quantity of another yellow compound separated out gradually. This was collected, washed with rectified spirit and then repeatedly crystallised from aqueous pyridine, till the m.p. became constant at $265-67^{\circ}$. This substance, which has been named tambulol, is insoluble in most organic solvents. The yield is 0.2 g. from 12 kg. of fruits. (Found in samples dried at $140-45^{\circ}$ in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 : Sample I gave C, 52.95; H, 4.64. Sample II gave C, 52.01; H, 4.39 per cent). Tambulol is soluble in aqueous alkali and the alkaline solution has no reducing action on *o*-dinitrobenzene. Concentrated hydrochloric acid dissolves it in the cold forming an orange solution, which does not deepen on treatment with alcohol and metallic magnesium. The *acetyl* derivative, prepared in the usual manner, crystallised from ether-petroleum ether in flakes, m.p. 120° (not sharp).

Acetyltambulin.—0.1 G. of tambulin, 3 c.c. of acetic anhydride and a drop of pyridine were refluxed for 3 hours. The product was cooled, diluted with 20 c.c. of ether and filtered. The filtrate was freed from ether, acetic anhydride, etc., in vacuum and the brown residue was taken up in benzene, charcoaled, concentrated and carefully diluted with petroleum ether. The colourless crystals were collected next day and washed with petroleum ether, m.p. $160-61^{\circ}$. (Found: C, 61.31; H, 4.60; OMe, 21.19. $C_{22}H_{20}O_8$ requires C, 61.69; H, 4.67; OMe, 21.73 per cent).

Hydrolysis of Tambulin.—Tambulin (0.2 g.) was refluxed on the water-bath for 10 hours with alcoholic potash (20 %, 10 c.c.). The red solution was freed from alcohol under diminished pressure and the residue taken up with about 10 c.c. of water. The solution was then saturated with carbon dioxide at 0° when a yellow slimy precipitate separated out. This was filtered off and the clear filtrate was twice shaken up with small quantities of ether.

The brown-red solution was then concentrated on the water-bath and then acidified with hydrochloric acid. The greyish white precipitate was collected, washed with a little ice-cold water, dried and then sublimed in vacuum at $110\text{--}20^\circ/0\cdot05$ mm. The sublimate formed long colourless needles, m.p. $179\text{--}80^\circ$, from dilute alcohol. (Found: C, 62.90; H, 5.35; OMe, 19.75. Calc. for $\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{O}_3$: C, 63.17; H, 5.26; OMe, 20.40 per cent). Mixed with a specimen of anisic acid, m.p. $180\text{--}81^\circ$, there was hardly any depression of m.p. The physical properties of both the compounds were similar. It is therefore anisic acid.

Dimethyltambulin (Tambulin Dimethyl Ether).—Tambulin (0.1 g.) dissolved in dry pure methyl alcohol (20 c.c.) was cooled in ice. To this was added a solution of diazomethane in ether (nearly double the calculated quantity) and the mixture was allowed to stand for 2 days at room temperature. Solvents were then distilled off from the yellow solution and the residue crystallised from dilute methyl alcohol in cream-coloured needles, m.p. $154\text{--}55^\circ$. It was then distilled in high vacuum ($210\text{--}20^\circ/0\cdot05$ mm.) and crystallised from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether as cream-coloured prisms, m.p. 160° . (Found: C, 64.55; H, 5.60; OMe, 41.42. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_7$ requires C, 64.52; H, 5.38; OMe, 41.67 per cent). The ether is insoluble in cold aqueous alkali and does not give any colour with ferric chloride in alcohol. Concentrated nitric acid produces a blood-red colour.

Demethylation of Tambulin.—Tambulin (0.05 g.) was dissolved in the minimum quantity of hot phenol and then mixed with hydriodic acid (d 1.7; 5 c.c.). The mixture was heated for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours at 130° . The product was then poured into 12 c.c. of water containing a little sodium bisulphite. The yellow-orange precipitate was collected, washed with water and dried. A portion of the brown product was dissolved in alcohol and treated with a very small quantity of freshly prepared sodium amalgam. The solution immediately turned light brown and a bluish green flocky precipitate gradually appeared. No attempt was made to isolate the demethylated compound in a pure condition as we had not enough tambulin at our disposal.

The C-H estimations recorded in this paper have been carried out according to Pregl's method by Mr. N. Ghosh, M.Sc., to whom we offer our best thanks.